

A CHATGPT QUERY TEMPLATE

The JSON template used to query ChatGPT is shown below. Note that when defining transitions in the JSON, external transitions have "wait for input" as their "transition type" and internal transitions have "automatic after * seconds" as their "transition type".

```
{
  "model struct types": [
    {"name": "", "elements": ""}
  ],
  "state variables": [
    {"name": "", "type": ""}
  ],
  "input ports": [
    {"name": "", "type": ""}
  ],
  "output ports": [
    {"name": "", "type": "" , "description": ""}
  ],
  "functions used in model": [
    {"function header": "", "function body": "", "description": ""}
  ],
  "transitions": [
    {"currentState": "", "transition type": "wait for input",
"condition": "*.received", "nextState": "", "state variable
update": "", "TRANSITION SPECIFIC OUTPUT(S)": ""},
    {"currentState": "", "transition type": "automatic after *
seconds", "condition": "", "nextState": "", "state
variable update": "", "TRANSITION SPECIFIC OUTPUT(S)": ""}
  ],
  "question": [
    { "m": "Above is a description of my state machine in JSON
format. Can you please provide me with * test cases?\n\nThe input data
MUST be in the form:\nInput Data: {Input_Port_Name{(input time), [input
value]}}\n\nIF there are expected outputs, they MUST be in the
form:\nExpected Outputs: {Output_Port_Name{(output sequence), [expected
output]}}\n\nREMEMBER: Outputs only happen if the transition
occurred.\n\nAnd finally could you also provide the state transition
path in the form of:\nState Transition Path: {initial state name,....,
final state name}\n\nALWAYS Assume that the initial state is a*."}
  ]
}
```

B VENDING MACHINE CHATGPT QUERY

```
{
  "model struct types": [
    {"name": "item_selection_t", "elements": "float price;
//represents price of an item; int item_id; //represents the id of an
item;"}
  ],
  "state variables": [
    {"name": "selected_beverage", "type": "item_selection_t"},
    {"name": "current_inserted_amount", "type": "float"}
  ],
  "input ports": [
    {"name": "i_beverage_selection", "type":
"item_selection_t"},
    {"name": "i_money", "type": "float"}
  ],
  "output ports": [
    {"name": "o_change", "type": "float", "description": "port
to ouput the calculated change which can be equal to OR greater than
0"},
    {"name": "o_dispense_id", "type": "int", "description": "port
to send the id of the beverage to dispense"}
  ],
  "functions used in model": [
    {"function header": "float calc_change(float x, float y)",
"function body": "return x - y;", "description": "returns amount of
change to be output on the o_change port"}
  ],
  "transitions": [
    {"currentState": "WAIT_FOR_SELECTION", "transition type":
"wait for input", "condition":
"i_beverage_selection.received", "nextState":
"COLLECT_CURRENCY", "state variable update": "selected_beverage =
i_beverage_selection.value", "TRANSITION SPECIFIC OUTPUT(S)": "NO
OUTPUT"},
    {"currentState": "COLLECT_CURRENCY", "transition type":
"wait for input", "condition": "i_money.received",
"nextState": "CHECK_AMOUNT", "state variable update":
"current_inserted_amount += i_money.value", "TRANSITION
SPECIFIC OUTPUT(S)": "NO OUTPUT"},
    {"currentState": "CHECK_AMOUNT", "transition type":
"automatic after 0 seconds", "condition": "if(current_inserted_amount
< selected_beverage.price)", "nextState": "COLLECT_CURRENCY",
```

```

"state          variable          update":          "none",
"TRANSITION SPECIFIC OUTPUT(S)": "NO OUTPUT"},

    {"currentState": "CHECK_AMOUNT",          "transition type":
"automatic after 0 seconds",          "condition": "if(current_inserted_amount
>= selected_beverage.price)",          "nextState": "OUTPUT_CHANGE",
"state          variable          update":          "none",
"TRANSITION SPECIFIC OUTPUT(S)": "NO OUTPUT"},

    {"currentState": "OUTPUT_CHANGE",          "transition type":
"automatic after 10 seconds",          "condition": "none",
"nextState": "DISPENSE_BEVERAGE",          "state variable update": "none",
"TRANSITION SPECIFIC OUTPUT(S)": "o_change.send(calc_change(current_inserted_amount,
selected_beverage.price))"},

    {"currentState": "DISPENSE_BEVERAGE",          "transition type":
"automatic after 5 seconds",          "condition": "none",
"nextState": "WAIT_FOR_SELECTION",          "state variable update":
"current_inserted_amount = 0",          "TRANSITION SPECIFIC OUTPUT(S)": "o_dispense_id.send(selected_beverage.item_id)"
    },

    "question": [
        { "m": "Above is a description of my state machine in JSON
format. Can you please provide me with 3 test cases?\n\nThe input data
MUST be in the form:\nInput Data: {Input_Port_Name{(input time), [input
value]}}\n\nIF there are expected outputs, they MUST be in the
form:\nExpected Outputs: {Output_Port_Name{(output sequence), [expected
output]}}\nREMEMBER: Outputs only happen if the transition
occurred.\n\nAnd finally could you also provide the state transition
path in the form of:\nState Transition Path: {initial state name,....,
final state name}\n\nALWAYS Assume that the initial state is
WAIT_FOR_SELECTION."}
    ]
}

```

C TEST DATA GENERATION

The full responses received from ChatGPT can be seen in the responses below. Note that TEST DATA GENERATION 1 is what is used for the case study.

TEST DATA GENERATION 1 -----

Certainly! Here are three test cases based on the state machine description you provided. These test cases will cover different scenarios to ensure the machine behaves as expected.

Test Case 1: Successful Beverage Selection and Exact Payment

Input Data:

```

- `i_beverage_selection{(0), [5.00, 1]}`
- `i_money{(1), [5.00]}`

```

****Expected Outputs:****

- `o\_dispense\_id{(1), [1]}`
- `o\_change{(0), [0.00]}`

****State Transition Path:****

- `{WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

Test Case 2: Successful Beverage Selection and Excess Payment

****Input Data:****

- `i\_beverage\_selection{(0), [3.50, 2]}`
- `i\_money{(1), [5.00]}`

****Expected Outputs:****

- `o\_dispense\_id{(1), [2]}`
- `o\_change{(0), [1.50]}`

****State Transition Path:****

- `{WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

Test Case 3: Insufficient Payment and Additional Insertion

****Input Data:****

- `i\_beverage\_selection{(0), [4.00, 3]}`
- `i\_money{(1), [2.00]}`
- `i\_money{(2), [2.50]}`

****Expected Outputs:****

- `o\_dispense\_id{(1), [3]}`
- `o\_change{(0), [0.50]}`

****State Transition Path:****

- `{WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

Notes:

- The output for `o\_change` is expected immediately after the `OUTPUT\_CHANGE` state, but the description suggests a delay. The test cases assume the output is generated as per the state transition without considering the delay in the description.
- The initial amount for `current\_inserted\_amount` is assumed to be 0 at the start of each test case.

TEST DATA GENERATION 2 -----

Given the state machine description, here are three test cases that cover various scenarios:

Test Case 1: Successful Beverage Selection and Purchase with Exact Change

Input Data:

- `{i\_beverage\_selection}{(0), [2.50, 101]}` - At time 0, a beverage selection is made with a price of \$2.50 and an item ID of 101.
- `{i\_money}{(1), [2.50]}` - At time 1, an exact amount of \$2.50 is inserted.

Expected Outputs:

- `{o\_change}{(11), [0]}` - At time 11, no change is needed as the exact amount was inserted.
- `{o\_dispense\_id}{(16), [101]}` - At time 16, the beverage with ID 101 is dispensed.

State Transition Path:

- `{WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

Test Case 2: Insufficient Amount Inserted, Additional Money Added

Input Data:

- `{i\_beverage\_selection}{(0), [3.00, 102]}` - At time 0, a beverage selection is made with a price of \$3.00 and an item ID of 102.
- `{i\_money}{(1), [1.00]}` - At time 1, \$1.00 is inserted.
- `{i\_money}{(2), [2.00]}` - At time 2, an additional \$2.00 is inserted to cover the cost.

Expected Outputs:

- `{o\_change}{(12), [0]}` - At time 12, no change is needed as the exact amount was eventually inserted.
- `{o\_dispense\_id}{(17), [102]}` - At time 17, the beverage with ID 102 is dispensed.

State Transition Path:

- `{WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

Test Case 3: Overpayment and Change Dispensed

Input Data:

- `{i\_beverage\_selection}{(0), [1.50, 103]}` - At time 0, a beverage selection is made with a price of \$1.50 and an item ID of 103.
- `{i\_money}{(1), [2.00]}` - At time 1, \$2.00 is inserted, which is more than the price of the selected beverage.

Expected Outputs:

- `{o\_change}{(11), [0.50]}` - At time 11, \$0.50 is dispensed as change.

- `{o\_dispense\_id}{(16), [103]}` - At time 16, the beverage with ID 103 is dispensed.

****State Transition Path:****

- `{WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

These test cases cover scenarios of exact payment, insufficient payment followed by additional payment, and overpayment with change dispensed, ensuring the state machine handles various types of transactions correctly.

TEST DATA GENERATION 3 -----

Certainly! Below are three test cases based on the state machine description provided. Each test case includes the input data, expected outputs, and the state transition path.

Test Case 1: Successful Beverage Selection and Exact Payment

****Input Data:****

- `{i\_beverage\_selection}{(0), [5.00, 1]}`
- `{i\_money}{(1), [5.00]}`

****Expected Outputs:****

- `{o\_change}{(11), [0.00]}`
- `{o\_dispense\_id}{(16), [1]}`

****State Transition Path:****

- `{WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

Explanation for Test Case 1:

1. The machine starts in the `WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION` state.
2. A beverage selection is made with a price of \$5.00 and an item ID of 1.
3. The machine transitions to `COLLECT\_CURRENCY` state.
4. \$5.00 is inserted, matching the price of the selected beverage.
5. The machine moves to `CHECK\_AMOUNT` and immediately transitions to `OUTPUT\_CHANGE` since the inserted amount equals the price.
6. After 10 seconds, the change of \$0.00 is output.
7. The machine then transitions to `DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE`, and after 5 seconds, dispenses the beverage with ID 1.
8. Finally, the machine returns to the `WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION` state.

Test Case 2: Insufficient Payment Initially, Followed by Additional Payment

****Input Data:****

- `{i\_beverage\_selection}{(0), [3.50, 2]}`
- `{i\_money}{(1), [2.00]}`

- `i\_money{(2), [2.00]}`

****Expected Outputs:****

- `o\_change{(12), [0.50]}`
- `o\_dispense\_id{(17), [2]}`

****State Transition Path:****

- `{WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

Explanation for Test Case 2:

1. The machine starts in the `WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION` state.
2. A beverage selection is made with a price of \$3.50 and an item ID of 2.
3. The machine transitions to `COLLECT\_CURRENCY` state.
4. \$2.00 is inserted, which is insufficient.
5. The machine moves to `CHECK\_AMOUNT` and then back to `COLLECT\_CURRENCY` for more money.
6. An additional \$2.00 is inserted, making the total \$4.00.
7. The machine moves to `CHECK\_AMOUNT` and then to `OUTPUT\_CHANGE` since the inserted amount is now sufficient.
8. After 10 seconds, the change of \$0.50 is output.
9. The machine then transitions to `DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE`, and after 5 seconds, dispenses the beverage with ID 2.
10. Finally, the machine returns to the `WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION` state.

Test Case 3: Exact Payment but No Selection Made

****Input Data:****

- `i\_money{(0), [1.00]}`

****Expected Outputs:****

- No outputs as no beverage selection was made.

****State Transition Path:****

- `{WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

Explanation for Test Case 3:

1. The machine starts in the `WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION` state.
2. Money is inserted without a beverage selection being made.
3. Since no beverage selection is made, the machine remains in the `WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION` state and does not proceed through any transitions or produce any outputs.

TEST DATA GENERATION 4 -----

Given the state machine description, here are three test cases that cover various scenarios of the system's operation:

Test Case 1: Successful Beverage Selection and Payment with No Change

```
#### Input Data:
- `i_beverage_selection{(0), [{price: 2.50, item_id: 1}]}`
- `i_money{(1), [2.50]}`

#### Expected Outputs:
- `o_dispense_id{(16), [1]}`

#### State Transition Path:
- `{WAIT_FOR_SELECTION, COLLECT_CURRENCY, CHECK_AMOUNT, OUTPUT_CHANGE,
DISPENSE_BEVERAGE, WAIT_FOR_SELECTION}`

### Explanation:
This test case simulates a scenario where the user selects a beverage
costing $2.50 and inserts the exact amount. The system should dispense
the beverage with ID 1 without returning any change.
```

Test Case 2: Insufficient Payment Followed by Additional Payment

```
#### Input Data:
- `i_beverage_selection{(0), [{price: 3.00, item_id: 2}]}`
- `i_money{(1), [2.00]}`
- `i_money{(2), [1.50]}`

#### Expected Outputs:
- `o_change{(11), [0.50]}`
- `o_dispense_id{(16), [2]}`

#### State Transition Path:
- `{WAIT_FOR_SELECTION, COLLECT_CURRENCY, CHECK_AMOUNT,
COLLECT_CURRENCY, CHECK_AMOUNT, OUTPUT_CHANGE, DISPENSE_BEVERAGE,
WAIT_FOR_SELECTION}`

### Explanation:
In this test case, the user first selects a beverage costing $3.00 but
initially inserts only $2.00. After the system waits for more money, the
user inserts an additional $1.50, making the total $3.50. The system
should then dispense the beverage with ID 2 and return $0.50 as change.
```

Test Case 3: Exact Payment with Delayed Money Insertion

```
#### Input Data:
- `i_beverage_selection{(0), [{price: 1.50, item_id: 3}]}`
- `i_money{(5), [0.50]}`
- `i_money{(10), [1.00]}`

#### Expected Outputs:
```

```
- `o_dispense_id{(26), [3]}`
```

```
#### State Transition Path:
```

```
- `{WAIT_FOR_SELECTION, COLLECT_CURRENCY, CHECK_AMOUNT, COLLECT_CURRENCY, CHECK_AMOUNT, OUTPUT_CHANGE, DISPENSE_BEVERAGE, WAIT_FOR_SELECTION}`
```

```
### Explanation:
```

This test case demonstrates a situation where the user selects a beverage costing \$1.50. The user first inserts \$0.50, then waits before inserting the remaining \$1.00. Since the total amount matches the price exactly, the system dispenses the beverage with ID 3 without any change.

```
---
```

These test cases cover scenarios of exact payment, insufficient payment followed by additional payment, and delayed money insertion, ensuring the system handles various user interactions correctly

TEST DATA GENERATION 5 -----

Given the state machine description, here are three test cases that cover various scenarios of the system's operation:

```
### Test Case 1: Successful Beverage Selection and Exact Payment
```

```
**Input Data:**
```

```
- `{i_beverage_selection{(t=0), [price=2.50, item_id=1]}`  
- `{i_money{(t=1), [2.50]}`
```

```
**Expected Outputs:**
```

```
- `{o_change{(t=11), [0.0]}`  
- `{o_dispense_id{(t=16), [1]}`
```

```
**State Transition Path:**
```

```
- `{WAIT_FOR_SELECTION, COLLECT_CURRENCY, CHECK_AMOUNT, OUTPUT_CHANGE, DISPENSE_BEVERAGE, WAIT_FOR_SELECTION}`
```

```
### Test Case 2: Insufficient Initial Payment Followed by Additional Payment
```

```
**Input Data:**
```

```
- `{i_beverage_selection{(t=0), [price=3.00, item_id=2]}`  
- `{i_money{(t=1), [1.00]}`  
- `{i_money{(t=2), [2.00]}`
```

```
**Expected Outputs:**
```

```
- `{o_change{(t=12), [0.0]}`  
- `{o_dispense_id{(t=17), [2]}`
```

```
**State Transition Path:**
```

```
-      `{WAIT_FOR_SELECTION,      COLLECT_CURRENCY,      CHECK_AMOUNT,
COLLECT_CURRENCY,      CHECK_AMOUNT,      OUTPUT_CHANGE,      DISPENSE_BEVERAGE,
WAIT_FOR_SELECTION}`
```

Test Case 3: Overpayment and Change Required

Input Data:

```
- `{i_beverage_selection{(t=0), [price=1.50, item_id=3]}`
- `{i_money{(t=1), [2.00]}`
```

Expected Outputs:

```
- `{o_change{(t=11), [0.50]}`
- `{o_dispense_id{(t=16), [3]}`
```

State Transition Path:

```
- `{WAIT_FOR_SELECTION, COLLECT_CURRENCY, CHECK_AMOUNT, OUTPUT_CHANGE,
DISPENSE_BEVERAGE, WAIT_FOR_SELECTION}`
```

These test cases are designed to validate the system's ability to handle exact payments, insufficient payments with subsequent top-ups, and overpayments requiring change. They also ensure that the system correctly transitions through its states and outputs the expected results based on the inputs provided.

TEST DATA GENERATION 6 -----

Given the state machine description, here are three test cases that cover various scenarios:

Test Case 1: Successful Beverage Selection and Exact Payment

Input Data:

```
- `{i_beverage_selection{(t=0), [price: 2.50, item_id: 101]}`
- `{i_money{(t=1), [2.50]}`
```

Expected Outputs:

```
- `{o_change{(t=11), [0.0]}`
- `{o_dispense_id{(t=16), [101]}`
```

State Transition Path:

```
- `{WAIT_FOR_SELECTION, COLLECT_CURRENCY, CHECK_AMOUNT, OUTPUT_CHANGE,
DISPENSE_BEVERAGE, WAIT_FOR_SELECTION}`
```

Test Case 2: Insufficient Payment Followed by Additional Payment

Input Data:

```
- `{i_beverage_selection{(t=0), [price: 3.00, item_id: 102]}`
- `{i_money{(t=1), [1.00]}`
- `{i_money{(t=2), [2.00]}`
```

Expected Outputs:

```

- `{o_change{(t=12), [0.0]}}`
- `{o_dispense_id{(t=17), [102]}}`

**State Transition Path:**
- `{WAIT_FOR_SELECTION, COLLECT_CURRENCY, CHECK_AMOUNT, COLLECT_CURRENCY, CHECK_AMOUNT, OUTPUT_CHANGE, DISPENSE_BEVERAGE, WAIT_FOR_SELECTION}`

```

Test Case 3: Overpayment and Change Required

```

**Input Data:**
- `{i_beverage_selection{(t=0), [price: 1.50, item_id: 103]}}`
- `{i_money{(t=1), [2.00]}}`

**Expected Outputs:**
- `{o_change{(t=11), [0.50]}}`
- `{o_dispense_id{(t=16), [103]}}`

**State Transition Path:**
- `{WAIT_FOR_SELECTION, COLLECT_CURRENCY, CHECK_AMOUNT, OUTPUT_CHANGE, DISPENSE_BEVERAGE, WAIT_FOR_SELECTION}`

```

These test cases cover scenarios of exact payment, insufficient payment followed by additional payment, and overpayment requiring change. Each test case follows the state transition path based on the inputs provided and the conditions outlined in the state machine description.

TEST DATA GENERATION 7 -----

Given the state machine description, here are three test cases that cover various scenarios of the beverage vending machine operation:

Test Case 1: Successful Beverage Selection and Purchase with Exact Change

```

**Input Data:**
- `{i_beverage_selection{(0), [3.50, 1]}}` - At time 0, a beverage with price $3.50 and ID 1 is selected.
- `{i_money{(1), [3.50]}}` - At time 1, an amount of $3.50 is inserted.

**Expected Outputs:**
- `{o_change{(11), [0]}}` - At time 11, after the OUTPUT_CHANGE state, no change is dispensed because the exact amount was inserted.
- `{o_dispense_id{(16), [1]}}` - At time 16, after the DISPENSE_BEVERAGE state, the beverage with ID 1 is dispensed.

**State Transition Path:**
- `{WAIT_FOR_SELECTION, COLLECT_CURRENCY, CHECK_AMOUNT, OUTPUT_CHANGE, DISPENSE_BEVERAGE, WAIT_FOR_SELECTION}`

```

Test Case 2: Insufficient Amount Inserted, Additional Money Added

****Input Data:****

- `{i\_beverage\_selection}{(0), [2.00, 2]}` - At time 0, a beverage with price \$2.00 and ID 2 is selected.
- `{i\_money}{(1), [1.00]}` - At time 1, an amount of \$1.00 is inserted.
- `{i\_money}{(2), [1.50]}` - At time 2, an additional amount of \$1.50 is inserted.

****Expected Outputs:****

- `{o\_change}{(12), [0.50]}` - At time 12, after the OUTPUT_CHANGE state, \$0.50 is dispensed as change.
- `{o\_dispense\_id}{(17), [2]}` - At time 17, after the DISPENSE_BEVERAGE state, the beverage with ID 2 is dispensed.

****State Transition Path:****

- `{WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

Test Case 3: Beverage Selection and Purchase with More Than Required Amount

****Input Data:****

- `{i\_beverage\_selection}{(0), [4.00, 3]}` - At time 0, a beverage with price \$4.00 and ID 3 is selected.
- `{i\_money}{(1), [5.00]}` - At time 1, an amount of \$5.00 is inserted.

****Expected Outputs:****

- `{o\_change}{(11), [1.00]}` - At time 11, after the OUTPUT_CHANGE state, \$1.00 is dispensed as change.
- `{o\_dispense\_id}{(16), [3]}` - At time 16, after the DISPENSE_BEVERAGE state, the beverage with ID 3 is dispensed.

****State Transition Path:****

- `{WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

These test cases cover scenarios of exact payment, insufficient payment followed by additional payment, and payment with more than the required amount, ensuring the system's response to different types of user interactions is verified.

TEST DATA GENERATION 8 -----

Given the state machine description you've provided, here are three test cases that cover various scenarios of the beverage vending machine operation:

Test Case 1: Successful Beverage Selection and Purchase with No Change

```
#### Input Data:
- `Input Data: {i_beverage_selection{(t=0), [price=2.00, item_id=1]},
i_money{(t=1), [2.00]}`
```

```
#### Expected Outputs:
- `Expected Outputs: {o_dispense_id{(output sequence=2), [1]}`
```

```
#### State Transition Path:
- `State Transition Path: {WAIT_FOR_SELECTION, COLLECT_CURRENCY,
CHECK_AMOUNT, OUTPUT_CHANGE, DISPENSE_BEVERAGE, WAIT_FOR_SELECTION}`
```

Test Case 2: Insufficient Amount Inserted, Additional Money Inserted

```
#### Input Data:
- `Input Data: {i_beverage_selection{(t=0), [price=3.00, item_id=2]},
i_money{(t=1), [2.00]}, i_money{(t=2), [1.50]}`
```

```
#### Expected Outputs:
- `Expected Outputs: {o_change{(output sequence=2), [0.50]},
o_dispense_id{(output sequence=3), [2]}`
```

```
#### State Transition Path:
- `State Transition Path: {WAIT_FOR_SELECTION, COLLECT_CURRENCY,
CHECK_AMOUNT, COLLECT_CURRENCY, CHECK_AMOUNT, OUTPUT_CHANGE,
DISPENSE_BEVERAGE, WAIT_FOR_SELECTION}`
```

Test Case 3: Exact Amount Inserted for the Selected Beverage

```
#### Input Data:
- `Input Data: {i_beverage_selection{(t=0), [price=1.50, item_id=3]},
i_money{(t=1), [1.50]}`
```

```
#### Expected Outputs:
- `Expected Outputs: {o_dispense_id{(output sequence=2), [3]}`
```

```
#### State Transition Path:
- `State Transition Path: {WAIT_FOR_SELECTION, COLLECT_CURRENCY,
CHECK_AMOUNT, OUTPUT_CHANGE, DISPENSE_BEVERAGE, WAIT_FOR_SELECTION}`
```

These test cases cover scenarios including exact payment, overpayment with change due, and a scenario requiring additional money to be inserted after an initial insufficient amount. Each test case follows the state machine's logic as described, with the expected outputs and state transitions based on the given inputs.

TEST DATA GENERATION 9 -----

Certainly! Below are three test cases based on the state machine description you've provided. Each test case includes input data, expected outputs, and the state transition path.

Test Case 1: Successful Beverage Selection and Payment with No Change

Input Data:

- `Input Data: {i\_beverage\_selection{(t=0), [price=2.00, item\_id=1]}, i\_money{(t=1), [2.00]}`

Expected Outputs:

- `Expected Outputs: {o\_dispense\_id{(sequence=2), [1]}`

State Transition Path:

- `State Transition Path: {WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

Test Case 2: Insufficient Payment, Additional Money Inserted

Input Data:

- `Input Data: {i\_beverage\_selection{(t=0), [price=3.00, item\_id=2]}, i\_money{(t=1), [2.00]}, i\_money{(t=2), [1.50]}`

Expected Outputs:

- `Expected Outputs: {o\_change{(sequence=2), [0.50]}, o\_dispense\_id{(sequence=3), [2]}`

State Transition Path:

- `State Transition Path: {WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

Test Case 3: Exact Payment, No Change Required

Input Data:

- `Input Data: {i\_beverage\_selection{(t=0), [price=1.50, item\_id=3]}, i\_money{(t=1), [1.50]}`

Expected Outputs:

- `Expected Outputs: {o\_dispense\_id{(sequence=2), [3]}`

State Transition Path:

- `State Transition Path: {WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

These test cases cover scenarios of exact payment, insufficient payment followed by additional payment, and successful selection and payment with no change required. Each test case follows the state machine's logic for processing beverage selections, handling payments, and dispensing beverages accordingly.

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Given the state machine description, here are three test cases that cover various scenarios within the described state machine:

Test Case 1: Successful Beverage Selection and Payment with No Change

Input Data:

- `Input Data: {i\_beverage\_selection{(0), [{price: 2.50, item\_id: 1}]}, i\_money{(1), [3.00]}`

Expected Outputs:

- `Expected Outputs: {o\_change{(11), [0.50]}, o\_dispense\_id{(16), [1]}`

State Transition Path:

- `State Transition Path: {WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

Explanation:

1. The machine starts in the `WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION` state.
2. A beverage selection is made with a price of \$2.50 and an ID of 1.
3. The machine transitions to `COLLECT\_CURRENCY` where \$3.00 is inserted.
4. The machine moves to `CHECK\_AMOUNT` and finds the inserted amount is sufficient.
5. After 10 seconds, in `OUTPUT\_CHANGE`, it calculates and outputs \$0.50 as change.
6. After another 5 seconds, in `DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE`, it dispenses the beverage with ID 1 and returns to `WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION`.

Test Case 2: Insufficient Payment

Input Data:

- `Input Data: {i\_beverage\_selection{(0), [{price: 3.50, item\_id: 2}]}, i\_money{(1), [2.00]}, i\_money{(2), [1.00]}`

Expected Outputs:

- `Expected Outputs: {o\_change{(12), [0.50]}, o\_dispense\_id{(17), [2]}`

State Transition Path:

- `State Transition Path: {WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

Explanation:

1. The machine starts in the `WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION` state.
2. A beverage selection is made with a price of \$3.50 and an ID of 2.
3. The machine transitions to `COLLECT\_CURRENCY` where \$2.00 is inserted first, then an additional \$1.00.
4. The machine moves to `CHECK\_AMOUNT` twice, first finding the amount insufficient, then sufficient after the second payment.
5. After 10 seconds, in `OUTPUT\_CHANGE`, it calculates and outputs \$0.50 as change.
6. After another 5 seconds, in `DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE`, it dispenses the beverage with ID 2 and returns to `WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION`.

Test Case 3: Exact Payment

Input Data:

- `Input Data: {i\_beverage\_selection{(0), [{price: 1.00, item\_id: 3}]}, i\_money{(1), [1.00]}`

Expected Outputs:

- `Expected Outputs: {o\_change{(11), [0.00]}, o\_dispense\_id{(16), [3]}`

State Transition Path:

- `State Transition Path: {WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION, COLLECT\_CURRENCY, CHECK\_AMOUNT, OUTPUT\_CHANGE, DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE, WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION}`

Explanation:

1. The machine starts in the `WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION` state.
2. A beverage selection is made with a price of \$1.00 and an ID of 3.
3. The machine transitions to `COLLECT\_CURRENCY` where exactly \$1.00 is inserted.
4. The machine moves to `CHECK\_AMOUNT` and finds the inserted amount exactly matches the price.
5. After 10 seconds, in `OUTPUT\_CHANGE`, it calculates and outputs \$0.00 as change.
6. After another 5 seconds, in `DISPENSE\_BEVERAGE`, it dispenses the beverage with ID 3 and returns to `WAIT\_FOR\_SELECTION`.

These test cases cover scenarios of exact payment, insufficient payment followed by additional payment, and payment with change due.